

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B029
 Date: 15 Jul 2004
 Take Off: 10:07:01
 Landing: 15:25:53
 Flight Time: 5h18m52

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Interception of North American outflow at low altitudes.

Operating Area: NW of Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	John Methven	Reading University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Jim Hopkins	York University
7	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
8	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
9	WAS	Lisa Whalley	Leeds University
10	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
11	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
12	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
13	PAN/ORAC/TDL/PSAP	Jim McQuaid	York University
14	Observer	Dominick Spracken	Leeds University
15	Mission Scientist 2	Steve Arnold	Leeds University
16	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B029 Track 15-JUL-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B029
 Date: 15th July 2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
100701		T/O	-.22 kft	089	
101904	103906	Run 1	14.0 kft	291	water/ice on RFC
110147	113339	Profile 1	14.0 - -.05 kft	009	descent, 500ft/min
110814		interrupt profile	10.6 kft	331	
110843		restart profile	10.7 kft	318	
113339	115450	Profile 2	-.05 - -10.0 kft	320	ascent, 500ft/min
113731		interrupt profile	2.1 kft		
113900		restart profile	2.2 kft		
115938	120243	Profile 3	10.0 - 8.5 kft	218	descent, 500ft/min
120349	121917	Run 2	8.5 kft	221	
122044	124959	Run 3	8.5 kft	312	
125453	131010	Run 4	8.5 kft	112	
131124	132414	Run 5	8.5 kft	165	
131500	132430	Heimann calcs, 10, 11, 12, 09			
132456	133052	Profile 4	8.5 - 5.5 kft	210	descent, 500ft/min
133119	134542	Run 6	5.5 kft	226	
134719	135256	Profile 5	5.5 - 3.0 kft	045	was 500 ft/min
135427	135941	Run 7	3.0 kft	047	
140106	141017	Run 8	3.0 kft	138	
141907	143602	Run 9	15.0 kft	164	
152553		Land	-.21 kft	272	
153000		final GPS posn 38 31.26N 28 42.98W			
153000		final INU posn 38 29.50N 28 43.31W			

B029 Track 15-JUL-04

B029: ITOP – Interception of North American outflow at low altitudes.

Mission Scientists: John Methven & Steve Arnold

Date: 15/07/04

Outline schedule:

06:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

08:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing

10:00 UT - Take-off

Location: NW of Azores

Aim: To intercept polluted plume which left US east coast in region sampled by NOAA P3 on 09/07/04. Sample contrast between pollution transported in Atlantic MBL and pollution transported just above the MBL into the Azores domain. (Forecast MBL height 3000ft or less). Return to Horta will include 45 minutes to sample air near Pico, for comparison with surface observations.

*spike in CO @ 10:42 @ 15ppb
O3 @ 80ppb.*

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to FL¹⁴⁰~~150~~. Transit to waypoint (31W, 41.5N). Transit should include 20 mins level run at constant altitude (out of cloud if possible) for calibration purposes. (30).
2. T+30 Profile descent to 500ft (500 ft/min) ahead of region of elevated US NOx to note MBL top (30).
3. T+60 Profile ascent to FL¹⁸⁰~~200~~ (500 ft/min) to note altitude of plume maximum (15).
4. T+75 Reciprocal descent towards altitude of plume maximum (~3000ft) (500 ft/min) (10).
5. T+85 Turn towards south-west to fly level run along filament orientation (30).
6. T+115 Profile descent @500ft/min to 500ft. (5).
7. T+120 Reciprocal, then profile ascent @500ft/min to 4500ft (10).
8. T+130 Level run to the northeast along filament orientation (30).
9. T+160 Reciprocal, then profile ascent to FL60 @ 500ft/min. (5)
- 10. T+190 Level run to southwest along filament orientation (30).
11. T+220 Ascend to FL100 (500 ft/min) (10).
12. T+230 Transit back to Azores. Include 20 mins level run (out of cloud) (30)
13. T+260 Perform racetrack around Pico for comparison with ground obs. (45)
14. T+305 Return to Horta.
15. T+315 Land.

zeroed NOx values lower than zeros

~ 11:32

11:59:38

12:03

forgot to catch P3 air

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...029**

 Date **15/07/04**

 Page **1** of **2**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:19:04	R1	FL140	291		Cloud free Uniform CO ~ 70 ppbv. Enter more moist air ~ 10:31.
10:39:06					O ₃ ~ 75 ppbv CO ~ 115 ppbv ~ 10:34
					O ₃ ~ 85 ppbv CO ~ 150 ppbv ^{High Nitrate aerosol}
11:01:45	P1	FL140 -100ft	007		500ft/min CO ~ 140 ppbv 11:06 Layer just below 12000ft.
Restart 11:08:43			330		CO ~ 40 - 60 ppbv continuous, 80 - 90 ppbv
					Rain @ 11:21 5000ft-6000ft layer
					CO ~ 120 ppbv ~ 4000ft. 42-3N 31.9W
					MBL top ~ 2000ft, not well defined
	P2	6000	330		CO ~ 110 ppbv right down to surface
Interrupt		000	050		
Resume 11:38:51					CO ~ 110 ppbv ~ 4000ft.-5000ft
					CO ~ 120 ppbv ~ 6800ft.-
					AMS
11:59:36	P3	FL100 -FL85	220		
12:02:42					CO > 200 ppbv.
12:03:48	R2	FL95	235		
12:19:23					Into CO ~ 150 ppbv => P3 sampled plume?
12:20:47	R3	FL85	325		
12:54:53	R4	FL85	115		Back towards main filament.
13:10:10					12:56 - CO consistently above 150 ppbv.
13:11:40					Salt towards max CO obs earlier.
13:24:14	R5	FL85	180		
					CO ~ 180 ppbv, O ₃ 70 ppbv ^{42-3N} ^{32-6W}
					Narrow feature.
13:24:55	P4	FL85- FL55	230- 240		
13:30:49					
13:31:17	R6	FL55	240		CO ~ 130 ppbv, O ₃ 40-50 ppbv
13:47:20					
13:52:54	P5	FL55 -3000ft	060		
13:54:25					
13:59:39	R7	3000ft	060		

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: 0029	DATE: 15/7/04	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: Aleda		PROJECT: TOP	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2		Argon/CO2		CO	
PRE FLIGHT	psi /	bar	psi /	bar	psi /	bar
POST FLIGHT	psi /	bar	psi /	bar	psi /	bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	R UN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 ()	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)
08:49:00	GROUND	-									
	Remarks: ZERO ON TEGCO NO - OFFSET 0.6 PPB										
10:16:						75.6	65	0.77	-0.74		
	Remarks: 1. LEVEL RUN FL 140.										
10:18:	FL90	R1	88.15	70.04	6174.01	78.58	64	0.59	-0.50	0.02	
	Remarks: OK SMOKE ~ 30 SEC BEFORE SMOKE OR R1. NO NOx NOx REMAINS IN KAW BEHIND CR										
09:3:	Ground	-	95.79	61.77	5916	299	69	69.7	18.7		
	Remarks:										
10:25:10	FL150					77	67.0	-0.30	0.40		
	Remarks: FL 140 NOx ZERO										
10:42:06						150.	78.				
	Remarks: FL 140.										
11:06:						130.	57	0.6	-0.5		
	Remarks: 500 FT - elevated CO + O3										
11:31:						105	39	0.66	-0.35		
	Remarks: in boundary layer ^{500 FT} starting ascent level run (FL ~ 3000 FT)										
11:59:						129	54	0.75	-0.54		
	Remarks: start of reciprocal descent.										
12:04:						114	61	0.64	-0.56		
	Remarks: FL 085.										
12:10:						~180.					
	Remarks: Elevated CO until ~ 12:24.										
12:42:26						136	54	0.77	-0.65		
	Remarks: level run heading north CO 'constant' since 12:24										
12:49:59						125	53	0.77	-0.61		
	Remarks: end of run - (commencing right turn)										
12:53:55						143	55				
	Remarks: heading south east @ FL 085										
13:11:05						137	55				
	Remarks: Run 5 - (trying to find high CO again)										
13:22:						~190	67				
	Remarks: elevated CO										
13:24:26						164	65				
	Remarks: start profile 4.1 starting coming out of plume so changed direction to further west to catch high CO again.										
:						136	43.				
	Remarks: end of profile 4										
13:31:19						134	43				
	Remarks: Run 6.										
13:53						132	42				
	Remarks: end of profile @ 3000 FT										
13:59						124	38.				
	Remarks: end of run										
14:01:						131	41				
	Remarks: run FL 30.										
14:20								0.7	-0.42		
	Remarks: NOx Cal. for ~ 6 mins										
14:36:02						149	72				
	Remarks: Run 9 end.										

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...029...

Date15/07/2004.....

Page1 of2.....

Video Tapes
V8
No. Ends FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	40° 05.40 N	40° 08.11 N
Long	031 11.40 W	031 10.38 W
Time	10:50:10	10:50:30
Status	✓	✓

DRS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HORACE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SATCOM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
10 01 35		Start Taxi						
10 07 01		T/O From Horta						
10 31 39		icing on RFC, note raining prior to T/O FL140		291	-2.5	3.8		
10 21 80		SATCOM call CCM to Peter CHAPPEL						
11 39 00		recommence profile 2 (not recorded on electronic flight summary) 2180 ft		036°				
11 51 46		TWC despoint trace following despoint trace but 20° separation						
12 05 00		HORACE crash						
13 05 00		SATCOM call CCM to Peter CHAPPEL						
13 11 40		Run 5 information incorrect on electronic flight summary 13 11 40 is the start of run 5						
13 15 00		Heimann cal (10) - for practice						
13 18 00		" (11) - " - "						
13 20 36		" (12) - " - "						
13 22 30		" 9 - " - "						

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B029 15/7/2004

Instruments

TWC COVER - NOT FITTED WHEN TWC PUT ONTO THE A/C
THIS MORNING. RAINING.

COCKPIT CONSOL AFT OUTBOARD PC FROZEN - REBOOTED

TRACKPLOT MAP: GEOGRAPHICAL DETAILS NO LONGER VISIBLE.

1 HORACE CRASH, BOOTED FROM NORMAL DRIVE

CAL CONSTANT FOR TWC

SEVERAL OCCURRENCES OF V. SLOW OR FROZEN HORACE DISPLAYS -
COCKPIT CONSOL AFT, COCKPIT CONSOL AFT, MISSED SUBMITT.

Aircraft